

Eco-evolutionary genomics of adaptation to climate change across contrasting terrestrial, marine and subterranean systems

Version 1

Description

Understanding how species respond and adapt to fast environmental changes is a major scientific challenge. Building on the success of our previous advanced computing projects (2024.07009.CPCA A1 and 2025.00006.CPCA A2), this proposal aims to extend those projects into an integrative computational framework that connects ecological modelling, demography, and natural selection across terrestrial and marine systems.

We will work on six main model groups that represent different ecological contexts and selective pressures: hares (*Lepus* spp.), weasels (*Mustela* spp. and *Neogale* spp.), blue sharks (*Prionace glauca*), pollinators (*Bombus terrestris*, *Syricta* spp., *Maniola jurtina*), an invasive fruit fly (*Drosophila suzukii*), and Azorean cave beetles (*Trechus* spp.). Our goal is to analyse genomic and ecological data to evaluate the adaptive potential of these species under environmental shifts, identifying genetic variation linked to resilience or vulnerability to climate change and other pressures, such as urbanisation.

High-performance computing (HPC) resources are crucial for this work, since the analyses require handling large whole-genome datasets and many parallel simulations. This project builds directly on our current experience with national HPC platforms, but it will scale up both data volume and analytical complexity to develop predictive eco-evolutionary models and open workflows that can be shared with the scientific community.

Funder

Fundação para a Ciência e a
Tecnologia, I.P. | FCT

Grant

ERC-Portugal

Researchers

João Pedro Marques (0000-0001-9834-1361), Inês Miranda (0000-0003-4773-2877), José Melo-Ferreira (0000-0003-4473-1908), João Pimenta (0000-0002-0989-8545), juliana sofia alves (0000-0002-2936-9886), Pedro Lucas Assunção de Sousa (0009-0008-7374-6678), João Monteiro Carvalho (0000-0002-1728-0075), André Godinho Lobo Pereira Viana (0009-0008-8586-1972)

Organizations

Associação BIOPOLIS - Rede de Investigação em Biodiversidade e
Biologia Evolutiva

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Eco-evolutionary genomics of adaptation to climate change across contrasting terrestrial, marine and subterranean systems

Description:

Understanding how species respond and adapt to fast environmental changes is a major scientific challenge. Building on the success of our previous advanced computing projects (2024.07009.CPCA A1 and 2025.00006.CPCA A2), this proposal aims to extend those projects into an integrative computational framework that connects ecological modelling, demography, and natural selection across terrestrial and marine systems.

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Organizations:

Associação BIOPOLIS - Rede de Investigação em Biodiversidade e Biologia Evolutiva

Contact: Marques João Pedro (joao.marques@cibio.up.pt)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P. | FCT

Grants: ERC-Portugal

Project:

3. License

License: AFL-3.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

FCT - Template in English

Eco-evolutionary genomics of adaptation to climate change across contrasting terrestrial, marine and subterranean systems data

Template: FCT - Template in English

Type: Dataset

1 DATA INFORMATION

1.1 What existing data will be re-used?

1.1.1 Will you re-use existing data for this project?

Yes

1.1.2 Which existing data you will re-use and under which terms of use?

NGS data produced in other projects

1.1.3 Describe the data type you will re-use

NGS data

1.1.4 Describe the format of data you will re-use

fastq.gz files

1.2 What data will be created or produced?

1.2.1 Will new data be created in this project?

No

1.3 What is the data volume?

1.3.1 How much data storage will your project require in total?

>1000 GB

2 DOCUMENTATION AND METADATA

2.1 Documentation

2.1.1 Indicate what documentation will accompany the data.

Each dataset will include a short README file describing the methods, software, parameters, and file structure. Scripts and pipelines will include comments and version information. Data will be organised in clearly named folders by species and analysis step, with version control managed through GitHub.

2.2 Metadata

2.2.1 Is there metadata associated with the data?

Yes

2.2.2 Indicate which metadata will be provided to help others identify and discover the data.

Metadata will include species name, sampling location and date, sequencing method, and analysis software. Standard formats (ENA/NCBI BioSample) will be

used, following FAIR principles. All datasets will have clear identifiers and will be deposited with their metadata in ENA, Zenodo and/or GitHub.

2.2.3 Please identify the metadata standard(s) that apply.

ENA Metadata Model

2.2.4 Please identify the controlled vocabularies that apply.

Study; Sample; Experiment; Run; Analysis; Submission

2.2.5 Please select the appropriate language for metadata.

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3 STORAGE AND SECURITY OF DATA AND METADATA

3.1 How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

3.1.1 Describe where the data and metadata will be stored during the project.

Institution networked research storage

3.1.3 Is there a policy in place for data backups during the project?

Yes

Monthly regular backups to the research group cloud and institutional storage

3.1.4 Please describe the type of backup.

Full backup

3.1.5 Please describe the frequency of backup.

Montly

3.2 Protection and security of sensitive data

3.2.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

Default security measures of the institution networked research storage

3.2.2 Please specify.

Access to the data will be restricted to the project owners and authorised group members. All data are stored on secure institutional servers at CIBIO-BIOPOLIS with user authentication and daily backups. No sensitive or personal data are involved. In case of incident, data can be restored from mirrored backups. Data protection follows the institutional IT and GDPR compliance policies.

4 PERSONAL DATA, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS AND OWNERSHIP

4.1 How will you handle issues regarding the processing of personal information and intellectual property rights and ownership?

4.1.1 Will you process and/or store personal data during your project?

No

4.1.3 How will ownership of the data and intellectual property rights to the data be managed?

José Melo-Ferreira (0000-0003-4473-1908)

Associação BIOPOLIS - Rede de Investigação em Biodiversidade e Biologia Evolutiva

All data generated in this project will be owned by Associação BIOPOLIS - CIBIO

5 DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

5.1 Long-term data preservation

5.1.1 How will data be selected for long-term preservation?

All data resulting from the project will be preserved for at least 10 years

5.2 Data available for re-use

5.2.1 What data will be made available for re-use?

All data resulting from the project will be made available

5.2.3 When will the data be available for re-use, and for how long will the data be available?

Data available as soon as article is published

Data will be made available as soon as the related articles are published. Raw sequencing data (FASTQ files) will be deposited in ENA, and processed data and

scripts will be released on Zenodo and/or GitHub. No embargo or exclusive use beyond publication is planned.

5.2.4 In which repository will the data be archived and made available for re-use, and under which license?

- European Nucleotide Archive
- NCBI BioProject

5.2.5 Please confirm if:

- The repository is registered in the re3data directory
- The repository is aggregated in OpenAIRE
- The repository is certified

5.2.6 Please indicate whether a persistent identifier will be pursued.

Yes

DOI

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

5.2.7 Under which license will the data be archived and made available for re-use?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

5.2.8 Describe your strategy for publishing the analysis software that will be generated in this project.

Generated code will be made publicly available on GitHub and/or Zenodo.

6 RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

6.1 Responsibilities and resources for data management

6.1.1 Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management?

- Inês Miranda (0000-0003-4773-2877)
- João Pedro Marques (0000-0001-9834-1361)

Associação BIOPOLIS - Rede de Investigação em Biodiversidade e Biologia Evolutiva

Postdoctoral Researchers

6.1.2 What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)?

A full week of the project will be dedicated to ensuring that data management follows the FAIR principles.

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